

What are the experiences, views and perceptions of patients, carers and clinicians of glucagon-like-peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RAs)? A scoping review protocol

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Background

Globally the number of overweight or obese people is increasing, with adult obesity doubling since 1990, leading to an estimated five million deaths from weight-related health conditions such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes and cancer,(1) with growing concern regarding obesity related conditions in lower and middle-income countries.(2)

Glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1 RAs), such as semaglutide and liraglutide, and the dual gastric inhibitory polypeptide (GIP) and GLP-1 RA, tirzepatide are drugs authorised in the UK by NICE for the management of obesity and/or type 2 diabetes mellitus.(3-5) A recent systematic review which summarised and critically appraised evidence arising from existing network meta-analyses (NMAs) evaluating the effectiveness of GLP-1 RAs for weight loss in obese patients highlighted that of these three types of GLP-1 RAs, subcutaneous semaglutide 2.4mg and tirzepatide 15mg were associated with the largest effects for weight loss at timepoints of six, 12 and 12+ months when compared to placebo.(6) Whilst tirzepatide and semaglutide were the most effective of these drugs for weight loss, they were also generally associated with increased risk of safety issues.(6) The review also highlighted a lack of NMAs comparing the efficacy and safety of tirzepatide and semaglutide 2.4 mg and recommended future NMAs should include trials to permit this. The review also addressed the need for longer-term trials to establish efficacy and safety of GLP-1 RAs when taken for longer than 72 weeks.(6)

Qualitative research provides the opportunity to gain insight into perceptions held regarding the of long-term efficacy, safety and acceptability of GLP-1 RAs, as well as the benefits and challenges associated with introducing this type of intervention for patients and health services.(7) One systematic review explores patient and staff views of barriers and facilitators to initiating, and adhering to, injectable treatments for Type 2 diabetes.(8) Only two of the forty-two included studies included participants with experience of GLP-1RAs, but neither of these explored views of that specific treatment. Another systematic review searched for quantitative and qualitative evidence to explore 'values, preferences and burden of treatment for the initiation of GLP-1 receptor agonists and SGLT-2 inhibitors in adults with Type 2 diabetes'.(9) Whilst the results from this review were primarily based on GLP-1RA, the findings were descriptive and do not provide an in-depth understanding of the experiences of patients and/or staff of receiving or providing a prescription for GLP-1RAs. Scoping searches indicate the presence of a small body of primary research which focuses on the views and/or experiences of patients or clinicians on the use of glucagon-like-peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RAs) to help control diabetes and/or promote weight loss. However, given the rapidly developing research landscape pertaining to this topic and changes in how these types of

medications prescribed and delivered, it is not certain the extent to which this existing evidence-base is useful to inform the current or future configuration and delivery of services. A scoping review will enable a better understanding of the key characteristics of the existing evidence base, and thus inform future commissioning of further systematic reviews and/or primary research.

Aim

To conduct a scoping review of primary evidence to better understand the quantity, nature and key characteristics of primary evidence which explores the experiences, views and perceptions of patients, carers, and clinicians regarding the use of GLP-1RAs for any indication.

Methods

There are six stages to undertaking a scoping review: (i) identifying the research question; (ii) identifying the relevant studies; (iii) study selection; (iv) charting of the data; (v), collation, summarising and reporting the results; and (vi) consultation.(10, 11) The methods section below outlines our planned approach to this scoping review according to each of these stages.

Identification of evidence

Research question

What is the quantity, nature and key characteristics of primary evidence which explores the experiences, views and perceptions of patients, carers, and clinicians regarding the use of GLP-1RAs for any indication?

Identifying relevant studies

Search strategy

A comprehensive search will be undertaken including both free text and controlled vocabulary searching, when available and relevant. We will use a validated search strategy as appropriate. We will search for both drug classes and individual drugs which will be based on products licenced in the UK as of May 2023, for any indication. The following databases will be searched from inception to present, with a qualitative search filter applied:(10)

- CINAHL Ultimate (EBSCOhost).
- MEDLINE (Ovid).
- APA PsycInfo (Ovid).
- Trial registries, CTRP (International Clinical Trials Registry Platform) from the World Health Organisation (WHO)
- Clinical trials.gov
- medRxiv
- ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global (Proquest).
- Google scholar using Publish or Perish (Harzing, 2007) software.

Additional relevant records will be sought by carrying out citation searching (forward and backward) of the included studies in Citation Chaser and Scopus. References will be managed using Endnote 20.2 (Clarivate Analytics).

Inclusion criteria

Population

Include

- Patients of any age who have direct experience of being prescribed glucagon-like-peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RAs).
- Carers who have direct experience of supporting someone prescribed GLP-1RAs.
- Clinicians responsible for the prescription of GLP-1RAs to patients of any age, with any condition.
- Clinicians responsible for supporting patient access to, or services delivering, GLP-1RAs.

Exclude

- Studies focusing on patients without experience of being prescribed, or taking, other types of medication for weight loss or diabetes control.
- Studies focusing on clinician experience of supporting delivery of other types of medication for diabetes control or weight loss.

Phenomenon of Interest

Include

- Patient experience, perception and/or views of being prescribed and/or taking GLP-1RAs.
- Carer experience, perception and/or views of supporting someone prescribed GLP-1RAs.
- Clinician experience, perception and/or views of prescribing, or supporting delivery of, GLP-1RAs.

GLP-1RAs can be prescribed for any reason, including control of Type 1 or 2 diabetes or weight loss.

Exclude

- Studies exploring the views of patients/carers/clinicians of taking, or supporting delivery, of non-GLP-1RA medication.
- Studies exploring the views of patients/carers/clinicians of taking or supporting delivery of multiple medication types, where findings specific to GLP-1RAs cannot be separated from experiences relating to other medication types.

Context

Health care or community settings.

Date of publication

No restriction.

Language

Include studies reported in the English language only. This reflects:

- The desire to avoid misrepresentation of participant experiences and/or loss of meaning during the translation process.
- Resource limitations within the study review team.

Geographical area

Any.

Study design

Include

- Qualitative or mixed-methods primary studies with qualitative data collection based upon interviews and focus groups and which use a clearly recognisable qualitative analysis strategy (e.g. thematic analysis, framework analysis).
- Qualitative studies using surveys or questionnaires with open questions as a data collection method.
- Studies focusing using qualitative analysis (e.g. content, thematic) to explore patient experiences posted on social media websites.
- Trial registry items or protocols with clearly specified qualitative component.

Exclude

- Qualitative studies using surveys or questionnaires as a data collection method based solely on closed questions (e.g. Y/N) or Likert-rating scales.
- Case studies (individual person and service/organisation level).
- Systematic or narrative literature reviews.
- Studies using quantitative methods to collect data e.g. randomized controlled trials, observational studies, cohort and cross-sectional studies.
- Conference abstracts.

Study selection

Two reviewers will independently apply the inclusion and exclusion criteria detailed above to a sample (e.g. n=50) of search results. Decisions will be discussed to ensure consistent application of criteria. The criteria will be amended if required to support greater reviewer consistency.

The revised inclusion and exclusion criteria will then be applied to the title and abstract of each identified citation independently by two reviewers, with disagreements resolved through discussion or referral to a third reviewer as required. The full text of each paper will be assessed in the same way. Endnote software will be used to support study selection. A PRISMA-style flowchart will be produced to detail the study selection process and reasons for exclusion of each full-text paper will be reported.

Charting the data: data extraction

Descriptive data will be extracted for each study by one reviewer and checked by a second. This data will include: first author, date of publication, title, focus/aim, country data collected within, population characteristics (including, experience relating to GLP-1RAs, health conditions, age, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, education, occupation), sample size, data collection setting, data collection technique (e.g. survey, interviews, focus group), type of analysis performed, , themes or ideas presented relevant to research question.

Collation, summarising and reporting of results

Key characteristics of all included studies will be tabulated and described narratively. Studies conducted with similar population groups, examining similar phenomenon of interest will be grouped together. The main findings will be presented alongside a visual representation of the studies included in the review.

Consultation and stakeholder involvement

Stakeholders will be provided with the opportunity to:

- Comment on search strategy and final protocol.
- Provide feedback on preliminary results.
- Comment on draft report.
- Support dissemination of findings.

We will seek to involve patients and members of the public in the conduct of this review by drawing upon the experience of our patient and public involvement group. Key areas for integrating their feedback during the review process include:

- Defining our research question;
- Developing the project protocol;
- Checking what level of information will be useful to the intended users of our review;
- Ensuring our review of available evidence is accessible to our intended audience;
- Providing feedback on preliminary findings and draft reports;
- Identifying opportunities for dissemination of findings.

Dissemination plan

We will produce a final project report in a style suitable for publication within the NIHR report library. We will also produce plain language summaries with our PPI group, which can then be used as a basis for other dissemination materials the research and stakeholder team feel are appropriate. These

dissemination materials may include a briefing paper, podcast, and blog post. Key outputs will be shared via the ISCA Evidence webpage, blog and Twitter feed.

The dissemination plan will be developed further as the findings of the review emerge to allow for the key messages and delivery mechanisms for each audience to be identified.

Anticipated resources

The estimated timeline is a minimum of 21 weeks, based on the four team members working full time on this review. This timeframe may be influenced by other requests for work by the Isca Evidence team. In such circumstances, the timeline will be renegotiated through discussion between Isca Evidence, our commissioners and government stakeholders.

This review will include input from all members of Isca Evidence. We will also seek to consult with review stakeholders, patients, and members of the public at key stages throughout the review process, as detailed in the 'Stakeholder involvement' section above.

Appendix A: Medline search strategy

Draft Medline search strategy

- 1 Semaglutide*.tw.
- 2 Ozempic*.tw.
- 3 Rybelsus*.tw.
- 4 Wegovy*.tw.
- 5 Liraglutide*.tw.
- 6 Victoza*.tw.
- 7 Saxenda*.tw.
- 8 Tirzepatide*.tw.
- 9 Mounjaro*.tw.
- 10 Exenatide*.tw.
- 11 Byetta*.tw.
- 12 Dulaglutide*.tw.
- 13 Trulicity*.tw.
- 14 Lixisenatide*.tw.
- 15 Lyxumia*.tw.
- 16 or/1-15
- 17 glucagon like peptid* one.tw.
- 18 "glucagon like peptid* 1".tw.
- 19 *Glucagon-Like Peptides/
20 exp Glucagon-Like Peptide 1/
21 19 or 20
- 22 glp-1*.tw.
- 23 or/16-22
- 24 interview*.tw.
- 25 qualitative*.tw.
- 26 experienc*.tw.
27 exp Qualitative Research/
28 24 or 25 or 26 or 27
29 23 and 28

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5. Excellence NIfHaC. Liraglutide for managing overweight and obesity (TA664) 2020 [Available from: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ta664>].
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